

**Peasant ballads of an imperial frontier:
Language, genre and representation in historical ballads of British Assam**

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Introduction

Existing studies on British India have significantly engaged with the peasant's experience of the empire. The studies have shown that, at one level, while the experience was disruptive and violent, it also produced new forms of peasant agency on the other hand.¹ It is in this context, as the studies have argued, that the question of peasant voice is important. With regard to reading the peasant voice, it would not be incorrect to argue that the main emphasis has been on the idea of the subject. That is, how to read in the peasant voice the articulation of peasant consciousness, whether in terms of nation, caste, tribe or class.² However, this has also brought forth a particular problem. If what one finds in the articulation is the intersectionality of nation, caste, tribe and class, then how would one understand the peasant as a category of analysis vis-à-vis colonialism. After all, nation, caste, tribe or class implies different conceptualisations and practices of social relations. In other words, while the peasant speaks, it would become difficult to ascertain (for the researcher) what is it that the peasant is speaking. As would be evident, at the centre of the above approach has been the idea that there is some kind of direct correspondence between a subject's intentionality and what the subject articulates in a given form. Any gap between the two can only be incidental, and can be overcome through better expertise. However, in this regard, there is one line of enquiry that existing studies have tended not to explore. Namely, rather than trying to read the peasant mind, is it possible to investigate how the peasant voice gets registered in a text; especially a

¹ Ranajit Guha, *Elementary Aspects of Peasant Insurgency in Colonial India* (New Delhi: OUP, 1983); Neeladri Bhattacharya, *The Great Agrarian Conquest: The Colonial Reshaping of the Agrarian World* (Ranikhet: Permanent Black, 2018). In the case of British Assam, see, Amalendu Guha, *Planter Raj to Swaraj: Freedom Struggle and Electoral Politics in Assam, 1826-1947* (New Delhi: ICHR, 1977).

² For example, Shahid Amin, *Event, Metaphor, Memory: Chauri Chaura 1922-1992* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1995).

text which emerges in the peasant context itself. After all, vis-à-vis the peasant, the starting point for the researcher in order to know the peasant mind would be the text.

Text, as we know, is not per se about an authorial voice. It is a site where multiple voices, or histories, or their traces, can be found in certain relations. Further, the multiple are not only constituted in relations of power. Through ruptures, they are also marked in limits.³ Such as, limits that a voice may experience in articulating its condition. In other words, what this highlights is that a subject's intentionality itself is not the text. As such, a key question would then be, how is it that the intentionality gets articulated in the text, or to what degree it gets or can get articulated. When such an approach is applied with regard to the peasant, it would mean two things. First, what the peasants speak is quite often available to us in certain narratives or forms. In that case, what can a reading of these forms tell us about the condition of possibility of the peasant voice articulating the colonial experience. Second, if the forms, as texts, cannot be necessarily reduced to the peasant's intentionality, then a question that would invariably arise is, what explains the peasant persisting with these forms.

In the paper, formulaic language with regard to the colonial peasant of British Assam, an imperial frontier, are considered an analytical problem in the light of the above approach. This has mainly meant investigating a particular problem. Namely, if the form being studied comprises a set of agrarian ballads, then how do we read what the peasant represented as colonial experience. In this regard, the ballads that are taken up in the paper are *Barphukanar Geet* (Ballad of the General),⁴ *Moneeram Dewanar Geet* (Ballad

³ For example, Pierre Macherey, *A Theory of Literary Production*, Translated from the French by Geoffrey Wall (London: Routledge & Kegan Paul, 1978). Also, Carlo Ginzburg, *The Night Battles: Witchcraft & Agrarian Cults in the Sixteenth and Seventeenth Centuries* (Baltimore: The John Hopkins University Press, 1983).

⁴ Suryya Kumar Bhuyan, ed., *Barphukanar Geet* (The Ballad of the General) (Guwahati: Pragjyotish Granthamela, 1954/1924).

of Moneeram Dewan)⁵ and *Doli Purana* (Ballad of To Throw a Clod of Earth).⁶ All the three ballads were of the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries. By the late nineteenth century, colonial agents, tea planters as well as the emerging Assamese bourgeoisie had commented on their popular agrarian circulation.⁷ They were oral ballads, and were collected between early to mid-twentieth century. Given the thematic nature of the ballads (dealing with actual nineteenth century historical events and characters), they have been often referred to as ‘historical ballads’.

A general outline of the ballads

The ballad *Barphukanar Geet* dealt with the Burmese invasions (1816-1826) of the pre-colonial kingdom of Assam, and the ensuing First Anglo-Burmese War (1824-26). Centred on the kingdom’s general, Badanchandra Barphukan, the ballad recounted the general’s rivalry with Purnananda Buragohaon (the Elder of the kingdom,), his journey from Assam to Burma to solicit military assistance to oust his rival, his return to the kingdom and subsequent assassination, and the eventual coming of the EIC army. Notably, throughout the ballad, the establishment of colonial rule was also referred to by the recurring formulaic use of the phrase, *Nohobor Hol*, or ‘what should not have happened, it has happened.’ The ballad *Moneeram Dewanar Geet* dealt with the historical figure of Moneeram Dewan, and his hanging by the colonial government on the charges of taking part in the mutiny of 1857. Similar to *Barphukanar Geet*, the establishment of colonial rule was referred to in the ballad by the recurring formulaic use of the phrase, *Nohobor Hol*. The third ballad, *Doli Purana*, centred on the event of a major peasant uprising of 28

⁵ Benudhar Sarma, “*Moneeram Dewanar Geet*,” (the Ballad of Moneeram Dewan) in Nagen Saikia, ed., *Benudhar Sarmar Racanavali* (Omnibus of Benudhar Sarma’s Writings), Vol. II (Guwahati: Publication Board Assam, 2014), 1070-74.

⁶ *Doli Purana*, Patharughat Souvenir (Mangaldoi: Darrang District Administration, 2017).

⁷ One of the earliest references to the circulation of these ballads in the peasant context was is Samuel Baidon’s account. See, Samuel Baidon, “Tea in Assam, with an appendix, ‘Rural Life amongst the Assamese”,’ (Calcutta: W. Newman & Co., 1877), Tr. 320 (j), Asian and African Collection, British Library, London.

January, 1894, that occurred at Patharughat, in the colonial Darrang district of British Assam. The uprising was against colonial land revenue enhancement.

Given that the ballads dealt with historical events in their geographical setting, an important aspect in this regard was the manner in which the peasant world got plotted in time and space. For instance, if questions of material life, mobility and circulations, ecology, or relation with state comprised the peasant world, they did not exist in the ballads in isolation from ideas of time and space. That is, these dimensions were plotted in order to constitute certain narratives around historical events and characters. The plotting also showed how these events and characters were operating in/through a certain geographical situatedness. Further, while some of these features were intrinsically related to the historical events and characters, there were also those which were generic to peasant life, especially the ones related to peasant material life. Nevertheless, in the ballads, such generic features too got plotted in the colonial experience. For example, in *Doli Purana*, it was on a tour of a weekly plantation *haat* (local market) where the peasants of the neighbouring villages were selling rice, ducks and eggs that the 'sahib' 'realised' that the peasants were not yet pauperised enough through high revenue rates to become landless, and thus were able to hold out against becoming landless plantation labour.⁸ However, such plotting was not a case of narrative realism. For instance, as mentioned earlier, a recurring phrase deployed as a trope in the ballads was '*nohobor hol, axom dex gusi bongal dex hol*', or (translation mine) 'What should not have happened, it has happened. The land of Assam has become a foreigner's land'. It was through the trope that generic features of peasant life and colonial experience were sutured and organised in the balladic plot. That is, if the colonial historical events were made meaningful in terms of breakdown and crisis in the generic features of peasant life, then formulaic tropes such as *nohobor hol* occupied an important place in communicating that relation.

How the peasant speaks: Structure of articulation

The preceding section has provided a very brief outline of the ballads. This section outlines the crucial question: what comprised the articulation of the peasant of an imperial

⁸ *Doli Purana*, 103.

frontier vis-à-vis the colonial experience. In this regard, for a genre that was not based on narrative realism, even though dealing with historical events, articulation mainly comprised a certain arrangement of style, motifs, tropes, and imageries in/through which the peasant voice got registered. The arrangement is understood here as the formulaic language of the genre. In that sense, formulaic language of an oral genre is not only about figurative articulation. For instance, one of the dominant explanations of why colonial peasant articulation in British India was figurative has been that, given the subordinate or subaltern position of the peasant, it was through a figurative language that the peasant could signify or critique, but in disguise, the relations of power that produced or sustained their condition. The disguise was a necessary condition for the class while articulating, given their dominated position. However, in the case of the ballads, the question of formulaic language was something more structural. It was about how the genre spoke, and why should the peasants have persisted with articulating their colonial experience through the given language of the genre.

While analysing this problem, i.e., what was the language of the genre, one would need to take into account two important considerations. One was the fact that the colonial experience of the peasants was an unprecedented experience. For instance, existing studies have pointed out how the colonial peasant was produced through a new land revenue category which did not exist in the pre-colonial period. Namely, the *ryot*.⁹ The *ryot* was a particular kind of peasant, one whose classification and relationship with the state a colonial invention. The other form of relation between the colonial state and the peasant was the opium economy. Along with British Burma, the peasant world of British Assam was produced as one of the largest consuming markets of opium throughout the colonial period. Opium revenue and agrarian land tax were the two biggest sources of colonial revenue in British Assam. This revenue was crucial in the expansion of frontier military infrastructure as well as the frontier's tea and mineral regime. After all, British capitalism did not finance its expansion in the frontier. As studies have noted, the crisis in

⁹ Bodhisatta Kar, "The birth of the Ryot: Rethinking the Agrarian in British Assam," in Neeladri Bhattacharya and Joy LK Pachuau, ed., *Landscape, Culture and Belonging: Writing the History of Northeast India* (Cambridge University Press, 2019), 38-65.

peasant life in the nineteenth and early twentieth century was fundamentally connected to these shifts in classification and changing relationship with the state, and the ruptures (often violent) that it entailed. Thus, one can see here what the recurring trope *nohobor hol* that got deployed in the ballads, as mentioned earlier, signified. However, there is also another consideration to be taken into account here. Namely, the condition of possibility of a peasant narrative form, not just recurring tropes, through which the peasant colonial experience could get articulated.

In this regard, one may argue that, at one level, the condition of possibility of a peasant narrative dealing with historical events and characters has to be looked for in the literary culture itself. For instance, between the sixteenth and eighteenth centuries, there were both performative and written textual cultures, composed in the Assamese language, that dealt with historical events and characters. Some of these performative cultures and written literatures, such as *oja-pali* and hagiographies, were part of the popular Neo-Vaishnava culture. Because of its proselytising nature, Neo-Vaishnava culture was practiced at the popular level, communicating with the masses. As a genre, *oja-pali* performative culture was practiced at a folk level too, dealing with historical events. In terms of written literatures, the genre of chronicle (*buranji*) was another major textual form that dealt with historical events and actors. Recent works on South Asian literary cultures have emphasised that the idea of oral and written, or *desi* and *marg*, etc., as separate watertight compartments of cultural practices would be improbable in the South Asian context. Historically, there has been circulation and borrowing between and within the domains. In other words, the oral-written continuum was a constitutive process in the production and practice of South Asian literary culture. This point is important with regard to the condition of possibility of a peasant narrative too, composed in the Assamese language, and dealing with historical events and characters. That is, in general, such a peasant narrative was otherwise possible because there were already existing genres as part of the oral-written continuum which dealt with historical events and characters.

However, if colonialism was an unprecedented experience for the peasant, what would be the peasant narrative form to deal with this unprecedented experience? In other words, if at one level, one finds that there was the possibility of a scope for peasant narrative to

deal with historical events and characters, there would still be the question at another level that what was the form in which that possibility got realised with regard to colonialism. This is because available or existing literary practice from the past did not have to deal with something like colonialism. To be noted here is that, even in the context of British India, this question has been generally less examined. In this regard, the argument briefly is the following. In terms of style of composition, i.e., the form and use of verse in their meters, the ballads drew upon pre-colonial performative genres (both folk as well as Neo-Vaishnava). In terms of narration and plot progression, i.e., how the verses were sequenced, while the ballads on the one hand drew upon pre-colonial performative genres, the notable point here is how the narration was based on the idea that something historical (and not mythical) in a concrete geographical setting was being narrated. Of the pre-colonial genres, such an idea can be traced mainly to the Neo-Vaishnava hagiographies and the chronicles. Both (Neo-Vaishnava hagiographies and the chronicles), however, were mainly prose compositions. In terms of imageries, i.e., how the images of events, places, actors, etc., were constructed, the idea was also already present in pre-colonial performative genres, as well as in the chronicles. Further, what might appear as references to the material life of the peasant world in the ballads, such as crops and vegetables, animals and birds, food, traders, soldiers, and monks, boats and boatmen, riverine world, paddy and grazing fields, etc., were features that could actually be found in pre-colonial literary practices too (performative and written). In that sense, one may argue, such features in the ballads can even be read as textual motifs when conceiving and representing an agrarian life.

However, the question is, if the ballads drew upon these already existing features and techniques to produce its narrative in order to deal with the colonial experience, did it enable coherence in the conceiving and representation of the object in question, namely the peasant's colonial experience? Were these features and techniques anachronistic vis-à-vis the object in question? This is because a general literary capacity to deal with concrete historical events and characters in their geographical settings, something that was in place between the sixteenth and eighteenth centuries, could be different from a capacity to deal with the colonial question, especially its unprecedented experience.

In this regard, one way of dealing with this issue is to investigate whether there was a certain observable arrangement at the level of textual structure. It is also thus that one might be able to observe what emerges from an encounter between pre-colonial genres and the nineteenth century historical context as far as peasant culture is concerned. While the point requires greater elaboration, only its broad outline is presented here. At the level of structure, one would find that the ballads were constituted through a series of opposite or inverse textual relations. Four such distinct series of relations were:

- (a) Breakdown of the existing order (but) Lack of its ideological critique
- (b) Unfolding of events (but in the) Form of memory
- (c) Description of events (but in) Figurative narrative
- (d) Peasant action (but) Neither to return to the past nor to envisage a future

As would be evident, the series is mainly relations of contradictions. An underlying factor behind the above order of inverse relations is that the first parts of the relations comprise the attempt to 'represent', while the second parts of the relations comprise the inability to 'represent'. In all the three ballads, the first parts and the second parts of the relations do not get resolved. The reproduction of the inverse relations across the ballads of the genre also comprises the specificity of the genre. Now though not formulated in such an order of inverse relations, some of the existing studies on the ballads too have indicated a few of these characteristics, especially the first.¹⁰ However, in such studies, the breakdown of the peasant agrarian order on the one hand and yet the lack of its ideological critique on the other hand has not been seen as a specific type of textual relation involved in the production of a textual nature. In such analyses, they remain as disparate features, framed more in the sense of strength and weakness of a text and not as a relation. In contrast, the advantage of the above formulation of order of inverse relations is that it not only allows studying all the ballads together, but also makes it possible to explore and

¹⁰ See, Udayon Misra, "Peasant Consciousness as Reflected in the Oral Literature of Assam: A Study of Two Assamese Ballads," in Tilottama Misra, ed., *The Oxford Anthology of Writings from North-East India (Poetry and Prose)* (Delhi: Oxford University Press, 2011), 164-185; and, Arupjyoti Saikia, "Oral tradition, nationalism and Assamese social history," *Indian Economic and Social History Review*, 49, 1 (2012), 37-72.

identify if there were deeper relations that constituted the genre textually, and whether the elements of the relations make sense only when seen through the inverse relations.

For instance, if the order of inverse relations comprised the structure of articulation in the ballads, it was produced by the crisscrossing of a two-fold condition: (a) While the ballads, as texts, carried in them literary features which belonged to contexts of literary production different from theirs, these features nevertheless also allowed them to deal with historical events of their own times. (b) The ballads, as texts, were however experiments outside the earlier narrative practices, and therefore they were yet to develop the tools (literary features) that would enable in them the capacity of ideological formulation vis-à-vis its context, i.e., the colonial context. It was both a complex and peculiar phenomenon. Yet, in order to explain the ballads, recognising this condition is important. That is, it is not enough to identify style, tropes, motifs, imageries, etc., of the ballads. Rather, it is important to identify an internal logic through which such elements were organised in an arrangement. Unlike the elements, the arrangement itself was not something that was already existing; it was a development specific to the nineteenth and early twentieth century British Assam. Further, the question of arrangement also points to another significant issue. Because the above nature of the arrangement cannot be traced to the medieval period, that it was historically specific to its time, therefore, what one is a witness to here is not merely the production of some ballads during the period. Rather, one is actually a witness to the birth of a particular genre of the times itself. In other words, if the peasant culture during the period found itself without the literary means to conceptually articulate its colonial experience, there nevertheless also developed in the course of this very lack a literary means through which the peasant's colonial experience could find a language; it was a language that also became constitutive of a new genre. It was also thus that a genre in peasant culture could become identifiable with the peasant's colonial experience. From an analytical point of view, all this perhaps refers to something important. Namely, if formulaic language was basically the language of the genre, i.e., a certain arrangement though formed through certain embedded limits of conceiving and representation of the peasant's colonial reality and how through the arrangement the peasant could access its colonial reality in the absence of any other literary means during

the period, then the issue before us is not whether the peasant spoke its mind; rather, it is in what kind of a language peasant consciousness could register its voice, and whether the language corresponded to the consciousness. In fact, has presuming that there ought to be such correspondence been a limitation in studying the peasant of British India?

While discussing the nature of articulation vis-à-vis colonialism that emerged from the peasant world, one also needs to point out that the peasant of British Assam was not only a colonial subject, but one of the imperial frontier. If by frontier we mean a type of space produced by colonial capitalism in the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, then the ballads provide some interesting clues to uncover in what way frontier making impacted the question of articulation of peasant experience? For instance, while colonial conceptualisation of the frontier was based on putting in place processes and institutions that rationalised the area as pristine and primitive, a focus on the ballads highlight the multiple levels of complexity through which frontier making can be understood. Such as, how the pre-colonial oral-written continuum produces a capacity to conceive and represent historical experiences in the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, and yet the embedded limits places constraints on an ideological conceptualising of the experience. This is striking because the second half of the nineteenth century had witnessed a series of peasant rebellions in British Assam with regard to opium and land revenue. As already mentioned, both opium and revenue policies in British Assam were structurally connected to colonial capitalist expansion in the region in terms of tea and rubber plantations, as well as minerals and forests. In other words, vis-à-vis colonialism, while peasant consciousness was an ideological reality, there was a limit to its realisation in a corresponding cultural form. Nevertheless, between the capacity and the embedded limits, there also got produced a language, a structural arrangement, that recurred across the ballads of the genres, and which also enabled the peasant to conceive in a certain manner the different historical instances connected to processes of frontier making (such as, wars, revolts, land relations or capital). This was an extremely creative cultural situation, but one produced by an objective historical condition.